

The Effect of Organizational Support on the Quality of Health Workers' Work with Awards as Mediation at Konawe Hospital, Southeast Sulawesi Province, Indonesia

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Abstract

Background: The quality of work of health workers is an important determinant in patient safety, service effectiveness, and hospital performance. At Konawe Hospital, the increasing service load and task complexity require strong organizational support and a reward system that is able to encourage optimal performance.

Objective: This study aims to analyze the influence of organizational support on the quality of work of health workers and examine the role of reward as a mediating variable in the relationship.

Methods: The study used a quantitative design with a *cross-sectional approach*. A total of 170 health workers were selected through proportionate stratified random sampling. Data were collected using standardized instruments and analyzed with Partial Least Squares–Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM) version 4.0. Model evaluation was carried out through tests of validity, reliability, path coefficient, mediation effect, and predictive relevance (Q^2 predict, RMSE, MAE).

Results: Organizational support had a positive and significant effect on awards ($\beta = 0.660$; $t = 14.574$; $\rho = 0.000$). Awards also had a significant effect on the quality of work ($\beta = 0.470$; $t = 7.066$; $\rho = 0.001$). The mediation test showed that the award was a significant mediator in the relationship between organizational support and work quality ($\beta = 0.310$; $t = 5.871$; $\rho = 0.000$). The Q^2 predict value of 0.417 for the award and 0.223 for the quality of work indicates the model's adequate predictive capabilities.

Conclusion: Organizational support has been shown to improve the quality of work of health workers, both directly and through the mediation of awards. Awards serve as an important mechanism that amplifies the impact of an organization's support on performance improvement. The implementation of a fair and structured award system needs to be integrated with a strategy to strengthen organizational support to improve the quality of services in regional hospitals.

Keywords: Organizational support; Awards; Quality of work; Health workers

1. Introduction

Health workers have an important role in determining the quality of hospital services. The quality of work of health workers affects patient safety, service effectiveness, community satisfaction, and the success of hospital accreditation [1]. In Indonesia, improving the quality of work of health workers is a strategic issue considering the increasingly complex demands of services and the high workload in public health facilities [2]. This condition is also experienced by

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Konawe Hospital, a type C regional referral hospital that has achieved plenary accreditation in 2023 and continues to strive to improve service standards through strengthening human resources. The number of outpatient, inpatient, and support unit visits that continues to increase every year shows the high intensity of services and work pressure of nurses in the hospital.

In this context, organizational support is an important factor that contributes to the quality of work of health workers. Perceived Organizational Support (POS) is defined as the extent to which employees believe that the organization values their contributions and cares about their well-being [3]. Various studies have shown that POS improves motivation, satisfaction, work attachment, and performance of healthcare workers [4,5]. When organizations provide support in the form of adequate facilities, fair supervision, clear communication, and policies that protect health workers, they have a more stable psychological condition to work optimally in the midst of high work pressure.

However, POS does not always have a direct impact on the quality of work. Many studies state that the relationship is mediated by certain psychological factors, one of which is reward. Within the framework of Social Exchange Theory, rewards are seen as a form of organizational reciprocity for employee contributions [6]. When health workers receive appropriate awards—whether in the form of verbal recognition, formal awards, incentives, or career development opportunities, they will tend to increase their commitment and performance in providing services [7]. In the health sector, awards have been proven to strengthen motivation and improve the quality of work of health workers, especially in the context of hospitals that have a high workload [8].

Recognition is also related to classical motivational theories, such as Herzberg's Two-Factor Theory, which states that recognition is an intrinsic motivating factor that directly increases performance and productivity [9,10]. Research in various countries supports this relationship. Research on nurses in the Middle East and Southeast Asia shows that awards have a significant influence on accuracy, precision of service, and patient satisfaction [11,12].

At Konawe Hospital itself, nurses work in a dynamic environment with high responsibility, ranging from emergency services, inpatient services, to referral services. Hospital data shows a high service burden and the need to improve the quality of human resources as one of the strategies to achieve the vision of being the best regional referral hospital in Southeast Sulawesi. In these conditions, health workers urgently need adequate organizational support and a fair and structured reward system to maintain the quality of work.

Although many studies have examined the relationship between organizational support and performance, research on the role of reward mediation in the context of regional hospitals in Indonesia is limited. Most studies focus more on job satisfaction, turnover intention, or burnout, while studies that place job quality as the main variable are rare [13]. In addition, research in areas with typical service characteristics such as Konawe Hospital which has a large area, geographical challenges, and high patient burden, is needed to provide a more contextual empirical picture. This research is expected to make a theoretical contribution in the development of a model of the relationship between POS, rewards, and work quality, as well as make a practical contribution to hospital management in designing effective interventions to improve the performance of health workers.

2. Method

The type of research is a quantitative research with a *cross sectional design*. The data obtained through surveys and statistically analyzed to determine the influence between variables, with analysis techniques planned through *Partial Least Square-Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM)* version 4.0. The number of samples in the study was 170 respondents with a random sampling technique using *proportionate stratified random sampling*.

3. Results

3.1. Outer Model

3.1.1. Validity test

Figure 1 Validity & reliability test model

Based on the results of the outer loading test, the results of each indicator show that it is valid > 0.70 , then all of the above statement items are declared valid.

Table 1 Reliability test

Indicators	Cronbach's alpha	Composite reliability (rho_a)	Composite reliability (rho_c)	Average variance extracted (AVE)
Organizational support	0.913	0.918	0.935	0.742
Appreciation	0.893	0.966	0.918	0.694
Quality of work	0.940	0.963	0.961	0.892

Source: Data processed -Pls.4 (2025)

Based on the results of the analysis, *Cronbach's alpha* and *composite reliability* values of all variables above > 0.70 , all variables are declared reliable for further analysis.

3.2. Inner Model

Figure 2 Hypothesis test

Table 2 Direct test results

Indicators	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Standard deviation (STDEV)	T statistics (O/STDEV)	P values
Organizational support -> Awards	0.660	0.665	0.045	14.574	0.000
Award-> quality of work	0.470	0.477	0.067	7.066	0.000

Source: Data processed -Pls.4 (2025)

The results showed that organizational support had a positive and very significant influence on the award with a path coefficient value of $\beta = 0.660$, a t-statistical value of 14,574 and a p value of 0.000 (<0.05), confirming the strong significance of this influence. The consistency of the sample mean value ($M = 0.665$) and the low standard deviation ($STDEV = 0.045$) confirmed the stability of the model. Thus, the greater the support felt by the workforce, the better the award they receive.

Furthermore, the award was proven to have a positive and significant effect on the quality of work with a path coefficient of $\beta = 0.470$ with a t-statistical value of 7.066 and $p = 0.000$ (< 0.05) showing a statistically clear influence, with data variation still stable ($STDEV = 0.067$). This confirms that adequate awards directly contribute to improving the quality of work of health workers.

Table 3 Indirect test results

Indicators	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Standard deviation (STDEV)	T statistics (O/STDEV)	P values
Organizational support -> Awards -> quality of work	0.310	0.318	0.053	5.871	0.000

Source: Data processed -Pls.4 (2025)

The SEM-PLS analysis shows that organizational support improves the quality of work indirectly through awards. The effect of this mediation was confirmed to be significant with a coefficient of 0.310, a sample mean of 0.318, and a standard deviation of 0.053 which showed the stability of the estimate. The t-statistical value of 5.871 and $p < 0.05$ confirm that the award plays a powerful mediating role in explaining how organizational support contributes to improving the quality of work.

3.3. Good of Fit Model (GOF)

Tabel 4 Fit Model

	Q ² predict	RMSE	MAE
Appreciation	0.417	0.774	0.529
Quality of work	0.223	0.890	0.808

Source: Data processed -Pls.4 (2025)

The results of the predictive evaluation show that the model has good predictive capabilities. The Q²predict value of 0.417 for the award and 0.223 for the quality of work, both of which are positive and indicate adequate predictive relevance. In addition, the RMSE and MAE scores for the award (0.774; 0.529) and quality of work (0.890; 0.808) are at an acceptable level of error. These findings confirm that structural models are not only statistically significant, but also quite reliable in predicting reward variables and work quality.

4. Discussion

4.1. The Impact of Organizational Support on Awards

The results showed that organizational support had a positive and very significant influence on awards ($\beta = 0.660$; $t = 14.574$; $p = 0.000$). These findings suggest that the greater the support an organization provides to nurses, the higher the perceived appreciation in the work environment. Organizational support, which includes management's attention, provision of work facilities, procedural clarity, and fair treatment, has been shown to increase the feeling of being valued and recognized by the organization.

Theoretically, the findings of this study are relevant to the Perceived Organizational Support (POS) framework which emphasizes that when employees feel the attention, protection, and support of the organization, they form a positive evaluation of the organization's commitment to their well-being. This perception fosters the belief that their efforts and contributions are recognized, thus giving rise to a sense of appreciation or appreciation from the organization as a psychological response to such support. In other words, organizational support creates affective conditions that reinforce the perception of appreciation [3].

The results of this study are also strengthened by a meta-analysis that POS is strongly correlated with reward practices in organizations, including financial, non-financial, and social reinforcement forms of reward[14]. In the context of health services, health workers such as nurses who feel supported by hospital leaders and institutions are more likely to report higher levels of appreciation, both in the form of recognition, promotion, and performance appraisal [4,15]. This support also creates *psychological safety*, which is a sense of emotional security for health workers to carry out their duties, innovate, and interact without fear of being blamed. This positive psychological environment ultimately reinforces the perception of appreciation for the work they do.

The findings of this study reinforce the literature, particularly in the context of Konawe Hospital, where strong management support has been shown to contribute to the increased appreciation felt by health workers. This has important implications considering that health workers are the spearhead of hospital services.

4.2. The Effect of Appreciation on Work Quality

The results showed that awards had a positive and significant influence on work quality ($\beta = 0.470$; $t = 7.066$; $p = 0.000$). These findings indicate that awards given to health workers, both in the form of recognition, incentives, verbal appreciation, and career development opportunities contribute significantly to improving the quality of work.

Theoretically, this relationship can be explained through Equity Theory, stating that when individuals feel they are treated fairly and rewarded according to their contributions, then they will improve the quality of performance as a form of reciprocation [16]. Awards create a sense of fairness and motivate employees to perform at their best.

These findings are also in line with Herzberg's Two-Factor Theory, which mentions recognition as one of the main *motivators* that improve performance through increased intrinsic motivation. Awards not only increase satisfaction, but also encourage proactive work behavior, discipline, and better clinical performance [9]

The findings are also in accordance with previous research, awards play a significant role in improving the quality of work of public service employees [10]. In the health sector, research shows that adequate rewards are positively related to nurse performance, especially in aspects of rigor, responsiveness, and professional ethics. Thus, the results of this study strengthen the empirical evidence that awards are an important factor that affects the quality of nurses' work, especially in the context of health services in hospitals [11].

4.3. The role of Reward mediates the organization's support for the quality of work

The results of the mediation test showed that the award significantly mediated the relationship between organizational support and quality of work ($\beta = 0.310$; $t = 5.871$; $p = 0.000$). These results indicate that organizational support not only improves the quality of work directly, but also through increased appreciation felt by nurses.

Theoretically, these results are in accordance with the Social Exchange Theory (SET) model, which explains that social relationships between organizations and employees are *reciprocal* [6]. When an organization provides support, employees reciprocate through improved quality of work, but the relationship is strengthened when the organization also provides adequate rewards.

In the framework of the Job Demands–Resources Model (JD-R), organizational support is a *job resource* that can improve performance results if followed by a good *reward system* [17]. Rewards serve as a motivational booster to maintain high performance. Thus, award mediation implies that organizational support becomes more meaningful when it is followed by recognition of employee contributions. The award mediates the relationship between POS and positive work behavior [18]. Meanwhile, research in the health sector, proves that awards strengthen the relationship between management support and the performance of health workers in hospital settings [19].

The findings of this study confirm that awards are an important mechanism that explains how organizational support can impact improving the quality of nurses' work. This indicates that managerial interventions should focus not only on the provision of support, but also on the integration of a structured reward system.

5. Conclusion

The support of the organization contributes significantly to the improvement of the appreciation and quality of work of health workers. Awards have proven to be important mediators that strengthen the influence of organizational support on the quality of work, thus explaining that the quality of work is not only influenced by structural support, but also by the form of appreciation given by the organization. These findings emphasize the need for integration between organizational support policies and performance-based reward systems to improve the quality of health care services. Further research is recommended to include additional contextual factors to gain a more comprehensive understanding.

Compliance with ethical standards

Disclosure of conflict of interest

This study has no conflicts of interest for either the respondents or external parties.

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